

Regulation of prostate cancer cell – macrophage – osteoclast interactions by TRAF6

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ABSTRACT

Inflammation is a contributor to prostate cancer progression. TRAF6, a key component of the pro-inflammatory NFκB pathway, is implicated in prostate cancer, bone remodelling and the immune response. However, its role in prostate cancer metastasis remains unknown. Here, we assessed the effects of pharmacological inhibition and genetic inactivation of TRAF6 in the growth, motility and ability of metastatic prostate cancer cells to influence immune and bone cells. *In vitro*, we showed TRAF6 knockdown and pharmacological inhibition using a novel inhibitor reduced the viability, migration and invasion of the human and highly metastatic PC3 and DU145 cells. Additionally, the exposure of macrophages to conditioned medium from TRAF6-deficient PC3 and DU145 or control cells treated with TRAF6 inhibitor reduced their ability to differentiate into osteoclasts. In contrast, TRAF6 inhibition had no effects on osteoblast viability, differentiation or ability to form bone nodules in the presence or absence of conditioned medium from PC3 cells. Our findings to date suggest that inhibition of TRAF6 shows promise in the treatment of metastatic prostate cancer. *In vivo* studies to test the effects of TRAF6 manipulation, alone or with chemotherapeutic agents, on the ability of prostate cancer cells to metastasise and interact with tumour-associated macrophages are ongoing.

Key words: Prostate cancer, metastasis, TRAF6, bone, macrophage, osteoclasts, immune cells.

1. Introduction

Constitutive activation of the pro-inflammatory NFκB signalling pathways leads to inflammation, which plays a major role in cancer (Xia et al., 2014). TRAF6, a key regulator of NFκB signalling, is implicated in immunity, bone remodelling (Lomaga et al., 1999) and prostate cancer (Sundar et al., 2015). However, the role of TRAF6 in prostate cancer metastasis to organs such as the skeleton has not been investigated. Here, we hypothesised that TRAF6 contributes to prostate cancer metastasis by orchestrating prostate cancer – immune - bone cell crosstalk. To test this hypothesis, we assessed the effects of pharmacological inhibition and genetic inactivation of TRAF6 on human prostate cancer cell growth, migration, invasion and ability to influence macrophage and bone cell differentiation *in vitro*. *In vivo* studies to test the effects of TRAF6 manipulation, alone or with chemotherapeutic agents, on the ability of prostate cancer cells to metastasise and interact with tumour-associated macrophages are in progress.

2. Methods

2.1. Western Blot

The protein expression of TRAF6 in a panel of human prostate cancer cells with different

metastatic abilities was measured using Western Blot (Idris, 2012). Briefly, cell lysates from human LNCaP, LNCaP C4-2, LNCaP C4-2B4, PC3 and DU145 prostate cancer cells were obtained and protein expression was quantified by Bicinchoninic acid protein assay. Denatured proteins (70 µg) were separated by electrophoresis using Criterion™ XT BioRad (12% Bis-Tris) pre-cast gels for 1.5 hours with 150 V and transferred to a polyvinylidene membrane. Membrane was blocked with 5% (w/v) milk in TBST and incubated overnight at 4°C on a rocker with the primary antibody. Next, the membrane was washed three times with TBST on a rocker with medium speed for 15 minutes and incubated with the secondary Anti-Rabbit antibody in a 1:1000 dilution of 5% non-fat milk in TBST on a rocker with low speed for 1 hour. The membrane was washed three times with TBST for 15 minutes and visualised using Clarity™ western ECL substrate chemiluminescent detection system on ChemiDoc™ Imaging System. Bands were quantified using Image Lab 6.0 software.

2.2. Metastatic behaviour assays

Cell viability was assessed using AlamarBlue® assay that measures cell viability by detection of reduction-oxidation reaction (Rampersad, 2012). Human prostate cancer cells PC3 and DU145

transfected with mock or TRAF6 knockdown or treated with the TRAF6 inhibitor 6877002 were cultured for the desired period and then incubated in 10% v/v AlamarBlue® reagent. After 3 hours, fluorescence was measured (excitation 560 nm, emission 590 nm) using a SpectraMax® M5 microplate reader.

Cell invasion was assessed using Transwell® assay (Justus *et al.*, 2014). Human prostate cancer cells PC3 and DU145 transfected with mock or TRAF6 knockdown or treated with the TRAF6 inhibitor 6877002 were cultured for the desired period and then were plated in serum free DMEM in the upper part of a 6.5 mm Corning® Costar® Transwell cell culture insert with polycarbonate filter pore size of 8 µm coated with Corning® Matrigel® Basement membrane matrix for 72 hours. Supplemented DMEM was used as a chemoattractant in the bottom part of the well.

Cell migration was assessed using wound-healing assay (Justus *et al.*, 2014). Human prostate cancer cells PC3 and DU145 transfected with mock or TRAF6 shRNA or treated with the TRAF6 inhibitor 6877002 were cultured 24 hours and then the confluent monolayer was scratched using a P10 pipette tip. Migration was monitored by a time-lapse video for 14 hours with a Leica AF6000 Time-Lapse imaging system and the percentage of wound closure was calculated with T scratch software.

2.3. Bone interaction assays

To evaluate the effects of TRAF6 inhibition on the ability of prostate cancer cells to affect bone cell function, the mouse macrophage RAW 264.7 cells (osteoclast precursors) and osteoblast-like Saos-2 cells were exposed to conditioned media from PC3 and DU145 transfected with mock or TRAF6 knockdown in the presence and absence of the TRAF6 inhibitor 6877002. Osteoclast formation was assessed by TRAcP staining and osteoblast differentiation and function by alkaline phosphatase and Alizarin Red staining assays, respectively.

3. Results

3.1. Highly metastatic and osteotropic human prostate cancer cells express high levels of TRAF6

Western Blot in human prostate cancer cells revealed that TRAF6 expression is higher in highly metastatic prostate cancer cells PC3 and DU145 as compared to androgen-sensitive

LNCaP cells (PC3, 0.61 and DU145, 0.63 ; $p < 0.05$).

3.2. Pharmacological inhibition of TRAF6 reduced cell viability, migration and invasion in prostate cancer cells

Exposure of human PC3 and DU145 prostate cancer cells to the novel, verified TRAF6 inhibitor 6877002 *in vitro* reduced cell viability (IC50; PC3, 26.94±1.51 and DU145, 21.03±2.49), migration (PC3, 8.75% ($p < 0.01$) and DU145, 26.52%) and invasion (PC3, 51.8% and DU145, 17.52%; $p < 0.05$).

3.3. Genetic inactivation of TRAF6 reduced cell viability, migration and invasion in prostate cancer cells

TRAF6 knockdown in human PC3 and DU145 prostate cancer cells reduced cell viability (PC3, 54.61% and DU145, 67.32%; $p < 0.0001$), migration (PC3, 25.76% and DU145, 20.18%; $p < 0.05$) and invasion (PC3, 35.2%, $p < 0.01$) *in vitro*.

3.4. TRAF6 inhibition reduced prostate cancer cell - macrophage - osteoclast interactions *in vitro*

Exposure of mouse macrophage RAW 264.7 cells to conditioned medium from PC3 and DU145 deficient in TRAF6 reduced osteoclast formation (PC3 14.12% and DU145 19.1%). Additionally, exposure of RAW 264.7 macrophage cells to the novel, verified TRAF6 inhibitor 6877002 in the presence of conditioned medium from PC3 and DU145 reduced osteoclast formation (PC3, 24.75% and DU145 20.86%; $p \leq 0.0001$).

3.5. TRAF6 inhibition had no effect on osteoblast maturation *in vitro*

Moreover, exposure of the human osteoblast-like cells Saos-2 to conditioned medium from PC3 deficient in TRAF6 with and without the novel, verified TRAF6 inhibitor 6877002 had no effect on osteoblast differentiation and viability *in vitro*.

4. Summary

Our findings to date show that TRAF6 inhibition disrupts the interaction between prostate cancer cells and macrophage and bone cells that are present in the tumour environment *in vitro*. This suggests that drugs that inhibit TRAF6 show promise for treating skeletal-related events associated with advanced prostate cancer.

5. Future and ongoing work

In vitro studies to assess the effects of TRAF6 inhibition on the interaction between tumour-associated macrophages and prostate cancer cells are ongoing. As a future perspective, we will carry out a number of *in vivo* studies to test the effects of a new generation of novel, verified TRAF6 inhibitors, alone or in combination with a chemotherapeutic agent, on the ability of prostate cancer cells to metastasise and to interact with tumour-associated macrophages in preclinical models of human and mouse prostate cancer.

6. References

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